

FEASIBILITY OF USING TEXTILE REINFORCED CONCRETE WITH POLYMER- AND MINERAL-IMPREGNATED CARBON FIBER TEXTILE AS EXTERNAL STRENGTHENING OF STEEL REINFORCED CONCRETE (RC) BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, the strengthening of existing steel reinforced concrete (RC) elements is a common practice. Textile Reinforced Concrete (TRC) is a cementitious matrix with fabric reinforcements that exhibits elevated mechanical properties/selfweigh ratio, thus being suitable for strengthening purposes. Carbon fabrics present elevated mechanical and durability properties, but poor adhesion towards cementitious matrices. The use of polymeric coatings is a well establish method to improve this bond and the composite performance. The use of mineral impregnations is a very promisor method to enhance the bond of carbon fabrics towards cementitious matrix, even at elevated temperatures. The present research evaluates the feasibility of a TRC with polymer- and mineral-impregnated carbon fabrics as flexural strengthening of RC beams. Different strengthening protocols were investigated. The results indicate that, with the proper strengthening protocol, the carbon TRC strengthening is effective in enhancing the RC beams ultimate load.

KEYWORDS

Carbon fabric; Flexural strengthening; Strengthening methods; Substrate preparation; Steel reinforced concrete beams

INTRODUCTION

Steel-reinforced concrete (RC) structures are prone to suffer damages throughout their life cycle due to degradation issues or loadings originally not considered in the design. In addition, they can have their design purposes altered, resulting in additional loading conditions. From a sustainability point of view, demolishing and rebuilding such structures is not interesting, thus creating the need for their rehabilitation. Nowadays, there are several repair and strengthening methods, from traditional techniques, such as cross-section enlargement and external prestressing with tendons, to more recent fiber-based composite systems.

Textile reinforced concrete (TRC) (also referred to as *Fabric Reinforced Cementitious Matrix*, FRCM) consists of a cementitious matrix reinforced with one or multiple layers of fabrics made of different fibers, such as aramid, basalt, carbon, glass, or natural fibers (Bramshuber, 2006). This material presents elevated mechanical and durability properties. The textile reinforcements are non-corrosive (Peled et al., 2017); thus, low thin concrete covers are necessary, reducing the weight of the elements. The low weight and high mechanical and durability properties of the TRC make it an outstanding material to be used for the strengthening and repair of RC structures. Furthermore, cementitious materials are known to present elevated temperature resistance (Mehta & Monteiro, 2006). This characteristic and the compatibility between the TRC matrix and the concrete substrate are interesting advantages for the use of this class of material over other strengthening systems. Previous studies show the successful use of TRC as flexural strengthening of RC beams. Brückner et al. (Brückner et al., 2006), Larbi et al. (Si Larbi et al., 2012), and Verbruggen et al. (Verbruggen et al., 2014) demonstrated the enhancement of the load-bearing capacity and the serviceability of RC beams strengthened with a glass TRC. Ambrisi and Focacci (Ambrisi & Focacci, 2011) showed that carbon- and PBO-TRCs were able to increase the maximum load of RC concrete beams. Gopinath et al. (Gopinath et al., 2015)

demonstrated that a basalt-TRC strengthening was able to increase the energy absorption and ductility of RC beams under monotonic and low-cycle fatigue loading. Teixeira and Silva (Teixeira & Silva, 2020) observed an increase in the maximum load of RC beams strengthened with a curauá-TRC-like composite submitted to bending tests. Hadad et al. (Akbari Hadad et al., 2020) showed an increase in the ultimate capacity of RC beams strengthened with a carbon-TRC.

The mechanical behavior of TRCs depends on the properties of the concrete matrix, the textile reinforcement, and also on the bond between the textile reinforcement and the concrete matrix (Brameshuber, 2006). Carbon fabrics present elevated mechanical and durability properties, making them a suitable option to be used as textile reinforcement in the TRC. However, due to the hydrophobic character of the carbon, this material presents a low bond with the cementitious matrix (Nadiv et al., 2017). Additionally, the multifilament nature of the yarns that form the textile contributes to jeopardizing the bond and, consequently, the mechanical behavior of the carbon TRC composites (Peled et al., 2008). Polymeric impregnations are commonly used to fill the spaces between the multifilaments, anchoring all of them in the surrounding matrix and contributing to increase the bond performance (Donnini et al., 2016; Dvorkin & Peled, 2016). The main disadvantage of polymeric-coated carbon fabrics is regarding their use at elevated temperatures due to the intrinsic low thermal behavior of most common polymer materials (Donnini et al., 2017; F. de A. Silva et al., 2014; Xu et al., 2016). Once again, inorganic materials seem to be an appealing alternative due to their elevated thermal resistance. Dvorkin and Peled (Dvorkin & Peled, 2016), Peled et al. (Peled et al., 2015), and Nadiv et al. (Nadiv et al., 2017) demonstrated that micro silica fillers used as impregnation material of carbon yarns enhance the bond of the yarns and cementitious matrices. Schneider et al. (Schneider et al., 2018, 2019) and Silva et al. (R. M. de C. Silva et al., 2022) observed that Mineral-Impregnated Carbon Fibers (MCF) yarns with cement-based (C) and geopolymer (GP) suspensions were able to maintain a good level of bond towards fine-grained concrete matrix in temperatures up to 500 °C.

This study aims to investigate the potential use of carbon TRCs as an external strengthening material in RC beams. Three different carbon fabrics were assessed: a commercially epoxy-coated (EP) carbon fabric and two lab-developed Mineral-Impregnated Carbon Fiber (MCF) fabrics, one with a cement-based (C) and the other with a geopolymer suspension. For this different substrate preparation methods were performed, namely surface roughening and aggregate exposure, aiming to establish the best strengthening protocol.

MATERIALS

Textile Reinforced Concrete (TRC)

A fine-grained concrete with a mix proportion of 1:1:0.3 (sand: cementitious material: water by weight) was used as the TRC matrix. Portland cement CP II-F 32 from LafargeHolcim defined by the Brazilian Standard ABNT NBR 16697 (Brazilian Standard, 2018), and river sand with a maximum particle diameter of 1.18 mm were used. Fly ash from Pozofly[®] and silica fume from Tecnosil were incorporated as mineral admixtures. A superplasticizer, Glenium[®] 51 from BASF, with a solid content of approximately 30%, was added to obtain proper workability for casting. The average compressive strength and modulus of elasticity, obtained by compression tests on cylinders specimens with 50 mm in diameter at 28 days, are 70 MPa and 35 GPa, respectively.

As textile reinforcement, three types of carbon fabrics with different impregnation materials were evaluated in this work: a commercially available epoxy-impregnated (EP) carbon fabric, namely GRID Q85/85 – CCE – 21, from Solidian, and two lab-developed Mineral-Impregnated Carbon Fibers (MCF) fabrics, one with a cement-based suspension (C-MCF) and the other with a geopolymer-based suspension (GP-MCF). Figure 1 presents the three carbon fabrics used, and Table 1 their mechanical properties. More information regarding the suspensions composition and the MCF impregnation process and fabric manufacturing can be found in (Schneider et al., 2019; R. M. de C. Silva et al., 2022).

Figure 1: Textile reinforcements with the overlap overlap for the external TRC strengthening. (a) C-MCF; (b) GP-MCF; (c) EP carbon fabric.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the EP carbon fabric according to the supplier and MCF fabrics according to (R. M. de C. Silva, 2023).

	Tensile strength (MPa)	Modulus of elasticity (GPa)
EP carbon fabric	2500	220
C-MCF fabric	1367 ± 160	220 ± 9.63
GP-MCF fabric	1591 ± 201	196 ± 0.650

Steel reinforced concrete

To evaluate the efficiency of the carbon TRC as flexural strengthening, steel-reinforced concrete (RC) beams were produced. An ordinary concrete with an average compression strength of 24 ± 3.82 at 28 days, obtained through compression tests on cylinder specimens with 100 mm in diameter, was used for the structural element.

All RC beams present dimensions of 1.2 m x 0.12 m x 0.15 m (length x width x high). They were designed to present a flexural failure. Steel ribbed rebars with characteristic tensile yielding strength of 500 MPa and diameters of 6.3 mm and 8 mm were used as stirrups and longitudinal reinforcement, respectively, resulting in a longitudinal reinforcement ratio of 0.56% and a shear reinforcement ratio of 0.35% (only in the regions with shear stresses). Figure 2 presents the details of the RC beams.

Figure 2: Schematic beam details and dimensions (dimensions in mm).

STRENGTHENING PROTOCOL

To evaluate the carbon TRC as a strengthening layer laminates with 1.0 m x 0.15 m x 0.02 m (length x width x thickness) were cast directly in the beam's inferior side, i.e., the side submitted to tensile stresses. Aiming for the joint mechanical work between the RC beam and the TRC layer, different strengthening protocols with varied substrate preparation modes, namely surface roughening (Patterned Roughing and Total Roughing) and aggregate exposure (Retarder Paper and Retarder Release Agent), were adopted. The summary of the strengthening protocols and the order in which they were performed is presented in Figure 3. In all cases, only the region in which the strengthening layer was going to be applied was prepared with the adopted protocol, see Figure 4, representing a practical situation in which the support regions cannot be assessed. One beam was kept without strengthening for comparison purposes (REF). Only one beam was tested for each strengthening protocol.

Figure 3: Summary of the adopted strengthening protocols.

Before being strengthened, all RC beams were pre-loaded to apply a certain level of damage, simulating practical conditions. The reference beam was also pre-loaded for comparison purposes. Usually, the design of RC beams is limited by the Deflection Serviceability Limit State (SLS-DEF), which limits the maximum displacement allowed in order to guarantee sensory acceptability to users and the correct functioning of all structural and non-structural elements (Brazilian Standard, 2014; European Standard EN, 2004; International Federation for structural concrete, 2012). Thus, the beams were pre-loaded to a maximum deflection of approximately 4.4 mm, which represents the maximum displacement allowed in the Deflection Serviceability Limit State (SLS-DEF). For this, four-point bending tests were performed after 28 days of the RC beams' casting, as described in the following section.

The strengthening protocols based on the manual roughening of the surface were performed after the pre-cracking process, while the ones based on the aggregate exposure processes were executed in the casting phase. The Pattern Roughing (PR) protocol consisted of the roughening of the beam surface where the strengthening was going to be applied with a hammer drill coupled with a bit of $\phi 13$ mm. Grooves of 20 mm width spaced between each other of 60 mm were produced, see Figure 4.a. The Total Roughing (TR) followed the same procedure as the PR with the difference that the entire region in which the strengthening was going to be applied was roughened. As this process was done manually, the TR protocol could be divided into two groups according to the depth and distribution of the resulting grooves. Figure 4.b shows the TR-I, in which the grooves present an average depth of 2.5 ± 0.596 mm and are uniformly distributed on the whole strengthening surface area. The TR-II presents grooves with an average depth of 3.22 ± 1.07 mm, and they are more concentrated in some regions and not uniformly distributed in the whole strengthening surface area, as shown in Figure 4.c. The other two methods used for the substrate preparation consisted of exposing the aggregates. For this, two commercial materials that delay the superficial setting time of the cement paste were used: a retarder paper WB-Paper Type "green" with an exposure depth of approximately 3-5 mm, from HEBAU, Germany, and a retarder release agent Ortolan-SR, from MC-Bauchemie, Brazil. In both cases, the retarder agent was applied in the mold before casting, as indicated by the suppliers. After demolding, the beams were washed with pressure water to remove the layer of cement that did not set. Figure 4.d,e present the beam surface with the exposed aggregates.

Figure 4: Strengthening protocols: (a) Pattern Roughing (PR); (b) Total Roughening - I (TR-I); (c) Total Roughening - II (TR-II); (d) Retarder Paper HEBAU “Green” (PHG); (e) Retarder Release Agent Ortolan SR (RAO).

For all strengthening evaluated, the TRCs were reinforced with one carbon fabric layer. To achieve the desired length of the reinforcement textile (1.0 m), overlaps of 140 mm were adopted as demonstrated in Figure 1. For the application of the TRC strengthening layer, the beams were placed upside down, i.e., with their tensile stress zone faced up, and the preparation of the substrate for the PR and TR beams took place. For all beams, the substrate was cleaned and slightly moistened, and a wooden mold with a strengthening thickness (20 mm) was assembled. The composite application consisted of a hand lay-up technique, in which a first layer of the fine-grained concrete matrix was placed, followed by the positioning of the textile reinforcement, and then a second and final layer of the fine-grained concrete matrix was poured over. After 24h, the mold was disassembled, and the TRC-strengthened beams were cured in the humid chamber for another 28 days so that the fine-grained concrete matrix could achieve its design strength.

BENDING TESTS

To evaluate the efficiency of the carbon TRC as external flexural strengthening of RC beams, four-point bending tests were performed in an MTS servo-hydraulic system with 500 kN load capacity. All beams were submitted to bending two times, a pre-load before the strengthening (first loading) and then up to a complete failure after the strengthening (second loading). All tests were controlled by displacement at a rate of 1 mm/min, and the same rate was adopted for the loading and unloading phases of the pre-load tests. Figure 5 presents the scheme of the setup for the bending tests. The beams were tested with an 1100 mm span, and the load was applied by two rollers 370 mm distant from each other. Both support and load application rollers had free horizontal displacement. Three LVDTs were positioned on the bottom of the tested beam aligned with the load application points and at the midspan to obtain the deflection values.

Figure 5: Scheme of the experimental setup of the beams four-point bending tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 6 presents the load vs. actuator displacement curves obtained from the tests, separated by batches. The Reference beam results were plotted for comparison to all batches. The measurements obtained with the LVDTs were not used in this initial stage because some failure modes altered their reading in more advanced loading stages. Table 2 shows the main results obtained. The *Increase of Maximum Load* is the ratio between the maximum load of the TRC-strengthened beam and the maximum load of the Reference beam.

Figure 6: Load vs. actuator displacement of the beams from (a) Batch 1 – PR-EP, PR-C, and PR-G; (b) Batch 2 – TR-I-EP, PHG-EP, and RAO-EP; (c) Batch 3 – TR-II-C and TR-II-G; and (d) Batch 4 – PHG-C and PHG-G.

Table 2: Main results obtained for the reference and strengthened RC beams.

Beam	REF	PR-EP	PR-C	PR-G	TR-I-EP	PHG-EP	RAO-EP
Max load (kN)	35.3	43.6	41.1	44.2	59.2	60.7	59.4
Increase of max load (%)	-	23.5	16.4	25.2	67.7	72.0	68.3
Beam	TR-II-C	TR-II-G	PHG-C	PHG-G			
Max load (kN)	43.2	43.5	56.2	54.3			
Increase of max load (%)	22.4	23.2	59.2	53.8			

- Batch 1

The first strengthening protocol adopted was the Patterned Roughing (PR). A total detachment of the TRC-strengthening layer was observed in the PR-EP, PR-C, and PR-G beams. Figure 7 presents the failure mode of the PR-EP beam as an example of the failure mode characterized by the TRC-strengthening layer total detachment. However, the strengthening layer did not completely detach all at once; first, it detached only on one side (Partial detachment), and, with the subsequent increase in load, there was a total detachment. The disassembly points can be identified as sudden drops in the load vs. actuator displacement curves (see Figure 6.a). Thus, the PR substrate preparation method was not adequate to guarantee a collaborative behavior of the TRC-strengthening layer and the RC beam. Nevertheless, even with the total detachment of the strengthening layer, it was possible to observe some evidence that the carbon-TRC presents the potential to enhance the load-bearing capacity of RC beams, as long as the strengthening protocol adopted is adequate to guarantee sufficient adhesion for the joint work of the two materials. The PR-EP, PR-C, and PR-G beams were able to achieve 23.5%, 16.4%, and 25.2% higher maximum loads, respectively.

Figure 7: Failure mode with total detachment of the TRC-strengthening layer of the PR-EP beam.

- Batch 2

A new batch of beams was prepared with different strengthening protocols, i.e., the Total Roughing (TR) and the aggregate exposure with Retarder paper (PHG) and Retarder Release Agent (RAO). This step was performed only using the EP carbon fabric for comparison reasons. The objective was to find the most suitable strengthening protocol to replicate in the RC beams strengthened with the TRC with the MCF fabrics.

All methods evaluated in Batch 2 proved to be effective in guaranteeing proper adhesion and, consequently, the joint work between the RC beam and the strengthening TRC layer. No detachment could be detected in the TR-I-EP, PHG-EP, and RAO-EP beams. Furthermore, it was possible to observe that the flexural cracks formed during the loading passed through the TRC strengthening layer to the RC beam corroborating that both concrete elements were working together (see Figure 8).

The TR-I-EP beam presented a flexural failure (Figure 8.a), and the PHG-EP and RAO-EP beams exhibited a more aggressive failure mode, with a combination of flexural and shear failure (figure 8.b and c). It was possible to observe a mechanism similar to the dowel effect in the level of the textile reinforcement in the TRC strengthening layer. Probably, the exposure of the aggregates was so intense that the shear resistance mechanisms of the RC beam were affected. The shear strength of an RC

element is governed by the transfer of the forces through the non-cracked zone, the transversal reinforcement capacity, the aggregate interlock, and the dowel action (Wight & MacGregor, 2012).

Regardless of the failure mode, all strengthening protocols from Batch 2 were able to enhance the maximum load of the RC beam in the range of 60 – 70%.

Figure 8: Failure modes of the (a) TR-I-EP; (b) PHG-EP; and (c) RAO-EP.

- Batch 3

To evaluate the efficiency of the TRC with MCF fabrics as external strengthening of RC beams, the Total Roughing (TR) method was selected based on the failure mode of the Batch 2 beams, and Batch 3 was manufactured. However, as previously mentioned, the roughing was performed manually, and in this case (Total Roughing, TR – II), it was obtained a different result from the first Total Roughing (TR-I), with deeper grooves, but not uniformly distributed in the whole surface. This difference in the grooves' distribution turned out to be crucial in the bond between the strengthening TRC layer and the RC substrate, and a detachment similar to what occurred in beams PR was observed (Figure 6.c).

Additionally, another point that could contribute to the poor bond between the two different aged concretes is the thickness of the textile reinforcement and the amount of matrix in the TRC strengthening layer. The MCF fabrics present higher thickness than the EP carbon fabrics due to the overlapping of the longitudinal and transversal yarns in the knots' regions. Since the thickness of the TRC strengthening layer was kept constant, this means that, in the TRC with the MCF fabrics, there is a smaller volume of the fine-grained concrete, which could also influence the adherence between the strengthening layer and the RC substrate.

- Batch 4

The methods based on the aggregate exposition create a substrate with more edges and hollows that could be advantageous for the strengthening based on the MCF fabrics due to the lower volume of the TRC matrix. Therefore, aiming to establish the best strengthening protocol for the TRC strengthening layer with MCF fabrics, Batch 4 was produced using the Retarder Paper (PHG) strengthening protocol. The Retarder Paper was selected based on the superior enhancement in the maximum load achieved with this strengthening protocol compared to the Retarder Release Agent for the beams in Batch 2.

The results obtained show that this strengthening protocol is adequate to guarantee a proper bond and, consequently, the joint mechanical work of the RC beam and the TRC with MCF fabrics strengthening layer. No detachment of the TRC strengthening layer could be observed, and the flexural cracks passed through from the strengthening layer to the RC beam. The C- and the GP-TRC were able to increase by approximately 50-60% the ultimate load of the RC beam.

CONCLUSIONS

The present work investigated the feasibility of different carbon-TRCs in the flexural strengthening of RC beams. With the proper strengthening protocol, all TRC-strengthened beams exhibited higher maximum loads, which confirms the feasibility of the three carbon-TRCs assessed for the flexural strengthening of RC beams. This enhancement was 67.7%, 59.6%, and 53.8% for the TRC with the EP carbon, C-MCF, and GP-MCF fabrics, respectively. The small difference in the load capacity gain makes the strengthening with MCF-TRCs a viable option to replace EP-TRCs, especially in high-temperature situations. The most suitable strengthening protocol depends on the type of carbon fabric used as textile reinforcement. For the strengthening with the EP-TRC, the Total Roughening of the surface proved to be the most effective substrate preparation protocol, as there was joint work between the TRC-strengthening layer and the RC beam without changing the failure mode. For the strengthening with the MCF-TRCs, the best strengthening protocol was based on the aggregate exposure with the retarder paper. The difference between substrate preparation methods depending on the type of textile reinforcement was associated with the amount of matrix in each TRC layer since the thickness of the TRC was kept constant and the MCF fabrics present a thickness considerably higher than the EP carbon fabric due to their manufacturing method.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge the CNPq and CAPES (Brazilian National Science Foundations) for partial financial support for this work.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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